

COVINFORM – Risk Framework Indicator Details

Definitions and reporting metadata for framework indicators

This document reports the data included in the COVINFORM Risk Assessment Framework. The Framework is composed of four domains (Threat, Vulnerabilities, Consequences and Resilience), and each domain is comprised of up-to four sub-domains, containing relevant indicators. This report provides information pertaining to the indicator attributes (e.g., reporting period, data source and format) and the scientific justification for inclusion. Each table also includes the direction of scale used to transform the indicators where 1 indicates that lower the value of the indicator, the better it is and -1 indicates that higher the value of the indicator the better it is. 'Better' is defined with respect to the indicator's sub-domain under consideration'. Where possible the original reporting format is described, or the reporting format that will be presented in the geospatial plots (i.e., cumulative COVID-19 case rate as opposed to daily). As described in the report [D2.7.](#), data was normalised for risk modelling activities.

Domain 1: THREAT (RISK OBJECT)

Sub-domain 1.1: Virus (cases)

COVID-19 Case Rate (weekly), Positivity Rate (%), Testing Rate

From the start of COVID-19 pandemic, the WHO's Emergency Programme implemented a global COVID-19 surveillance system¹. Widespread coronavirus testing, caused by infection with severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), allowed for monitoring of disease over countries and across population groups. SARS-CoV-2 surveillance was fundamental in understanding the evolution of the virus, the risk factors for severe disease and the impact of vaccination and public health and social measures.

To provide an overview of the epidemiological situation of the COVID-19 pandemic, health organisations reported weekly and daily COVID-19 statistics to track the number of COVID-19 cases, as per International Health Regulations (IHR 2005) requirements².

In addition to case rate, knowing the testing rate can indicate the level of surveillance activity in a country, and the proportion of positive tests can indicate the intensity of transmission.

Note: Guidance on testing was routinely updated as the pandemic evolved and testing capacity intensified³. Data users should be cognisant that testing strategies across European countries and the UK varied widely, from screening programmes to diagnostic tests in health care settings. In addition, total counts do not support cross country comparisons and should be analysed using per population rates.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Case Rate</i>
Reporting period	2020, 2021

¹ <https://www.who.int/emergencies/overview>

² <https://www.who.int/health-topics/international-health-regulations>

³ <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-2019-nCoV-SurveillanceGuidance-2022.2>

Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Cumulative
Definition and Reporting criteria	Cases per 1,000 population
Source/s	EU ⁴ MS & UK – Our World in Data
Direction	1

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Positivity Rate</i>
Reporting period	2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Cumulative
Definition and Reporting criteria	100 x Number of new confirmed cases/number of tests done
Source/s	EU MS & UK – Our World in Data
Direction	1

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Testing Rate</i>
Reporting period	2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Cumulative
Definition and Reporting criteria	Tests per 1,000 population
Source/s	EU MS & UK – Our World in Data
Direction	-1

Sub-domain 1.2: Variant of concern

Early in the COVID-19 pandemic, the number of ‘mutant’ variant viruses was low due to the relatively small number of infections, so there were less opportunities for mutations to emerge. For that reason, reporting of COVID-19 variants in national surveillance began in September 2020. Since then, the vast number of infections, has led to the evolution of multiple SARS-CoV-2 variants. For COVID-19 variants, clear evidence is available indicating a significant impact on transmissibility, severity and/or immunity that is likely to have an impact on the epidemiological situation. The COVINFORM project is interested in all variants of concern (VoC) over the course of the pandemic, that resulted in increased transmissibility⁵. These are labelled by transmission characteristics, either observed as community level transmission or dominant transmission (ibid.). For reporting, the WHO label (i.e., Alpha) is preferred as users will be less familiar with the variant code (i.e., B.1.1.7).

⁴ MS denotes Member States

⁵ <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/covid-19/variants-concern>

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Prevalence of Variants of Concern (VoC)</i>
Reporting period	2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily
Definition and Reporting criteria	% of Variants detected in the number of cases sequenced <ul style="list-style-type: none"> VoC - Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta, Omicron BA.1, Omicron BA.2 + L452X, Omicron BA.2, Omicron BA.4, Omicron BA.5^{6,7}
Source/s	EU MS and UK – Our World in Data
Direction	1

Sub-domain 1.3: Likelihood of development

Mobility Index

Because COVID-19 is highly infectious, decreasing social interaction and community movement have been important public health approaches to lower COVID-19 transmission rates. Following recommendations to limit movements, governments across Europe and in the UK imposed formal, stricter, and frequently legally mandated restrictions on people's freedom of movement⁸. These restrictions included "stay at home" orders, the closure of non-essential retail and schools, and the prohibition of sporting events and other public gatherings.

Google Community Mobility Reports aimed to provide insights into what changed in response to these policies. The reports charted movement trends over time by geography, across different places such as retail and recreation, groceries and pharmacies, parks, transit stations, workplaces, and residential homes.

Google mobility data shows how visitors to (or time spent in) certain places changed compared to 'baseline days'. Baseline day represents a normal (pre-COVID-19) value for that day of the week. It is the median value from the 5-week period prior to the pandemic, 3 Jan – 6 Feb, 2020.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Mobility Index</i>
Reporting period	2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily – Annual average calculated
Definition and Reporting criteria	Records change in mobility for the report date to the baseline day
Source/s	EU MS & UK – Google Mobility Data

⁶ Variants of concern as of 25 May 2022

⁷ SARS-CoV-2 variants of concern as of 21 Aug 2022

⁸ <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/the-territorial-impact-of-covid-19-managing-the-crisis-across-levels-of-government-d3e314e1/>

Direction	1
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International Trade

In a globalised world, trade can drive various factors that contribute to the transmission of viruses, such as a country's social interactions, economic possibilities, and mobility patterns. An early case study from Italy suggested that over time, confirmed COVID-19 cases had a strong correlation with trade (Bontempi, E., & Coccia, M. 2021). The results implied that total imports and exports are a complex indication of COVID-19 disease transmission that outperforms other widely used parameters, such as economic, demographic, environmental, and climatic characteristics, in explaining the COVID-19 spread (ibid.).

In the COVINFORM Risk Framework, we consider the degree of trade in which a country engages to be a probable indicator of disease transmission and the likelihood of development overtime. Trade data published by = measures the value and quantity of goods traded between the EU Member States⁹. Following the withdrawal of the UK from the EU on 31 Jan 2020, the UK were no longer legally obliged to share any trade data to Eurostat from the end of 2020. Pending an agreement on statistical cooperation between the EU and the UK, Eurostat will not publish any new data for the UK (ibid.). For this reason, a UK data source was selected for the COVINFORM project, so to evaluate the degree of change overtime within the UK. The UK data was converted from British Pounds Sterling to Euros using the average exchange rate for the year considered¹⁰.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>International Trade</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU MS - Exports and Imports in million (EURO) UK – Exports and Imports in GBP
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT UK – Office of National Statistics
Direction	-1

Other mobility data: International Sea and Air travel

As described above, mobility data has a significant impact on COVID-19 virus transmission. To capture the degree of mobility across countries, modes of transport beyond land travel were also integrated. Specifically, data regarding the number of passengers by sea or air, and the number of airports per capita are included.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Air Passengers</i>

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/6842948/11003521/Availability_of_UK_trade_data_after_BREXIT_FAQs.pdf/ce8cc509-8429-943f-5de3-a5d20cd33344?t=1614360113585

¹⁰ <https://www.exchangerates.org.uk/GBP-EUR-spot-exchange-rates-history-2019.html>

Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU MS – Number of International Air Travel Passengers and • UK - EU and Other International Terminal Passenger Traffic
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT UK – Civil Aviation Authority
Direction	1

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Seaborne Passengers</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU MS – Total number of International Sea Passengers UK - Total number of International and Domestic (to include Northern Ireland and British Isles) Sea Passengers
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT UK – GOV.UK
Direction	1

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Airports</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU MS – Commercial airports per capita UK - Commercial airports per capita
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT UK - Civil Aviation Authority
Direction	-1

Housing concentration

Overcrowded housing is a sociodemographic variable associated with increased infection rates from communicable diseases¹¹. It was widely observed that those of low socioeconomic status (SES), e.g., those with low household income, living in overcrowding dwellings and low education, were more vulnerable to COVID-19 morbidity and mortality (Khanijahani et al., 2021, Public Health England, 2020). Public health interventions to prevent and stop the spread of SARS-CoV-2 were slow to consider the risk of infection transmission for people living in overcrowded households and suitable interventions to reduce the risk of infection transmission (Soltan et al., 2021).

¹¹ WHO Housing and Health Guidelines: web Annex A. Accessed 15 March 2023. URL: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/275838>

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Housing Concentration</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU MS – Percentage of the population living in an overcrowded household • UK (England only)- Percentage of population living in overcrowded households. The data is an average for the 3 years from April 2018 to March 2021. This is to make sure there are enough households to be able to make reliable generalisations.
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT - EU-SILC Survey UK (England Only) – GOV.UK – English Housing Survey
Direction	1

Pollution

Scientists worked to identify the environmental conditions that might have aided the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. SARS-CoV-2 is an airborne virus, meaning the most common route of transmission is the spread of pathogens through the respiratory system by infected subjects and the penetration into the receiving host by inhalation.

For many viruses, atmospheric particulate matter (PM) would serve as a transport vector. The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) defines PM as a group of particles that have been dispersed in the air for long enough to be diffused and transported¹². PM fosters a microenvironment favourable to a virus' persistence, therefore it is possible that it boosted SAR-CoV-2 viral transmission in respiratory aerosol. Environmental pollution, specifically PM, was evaluated by numerous scientists as one of the potential key contributors to the spread of COVID-19 (Comunian et al., 2020).

Based on these premises, we decided to include the PM10 annual average of the mean daily concentration as a factor influencing enhanced virus transmission.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Pollution (PM10)</i>
Reporting period of interest	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Annual mean
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU MS & UK – PM10 annual average of the mean daily PM10 concentration

¹² <https://www.epa.gov/pm-pollution/particulate-matter-pm-basics#PM>

Source/s	EU MS & UK – European Environmental Agency UK – GOV.UK
Direction	1

Temperature

Other viruses, like flu viruses and other coronaviruses, are known to be affected by environmental factors. For example, high temperatures and low humidity reduce the transmission of respiratory droplets, preventing the spread of flu. High temperatures are also known to inactivate other coronaviruses in the air and on surfaces. The relationship with SARS-CoV-2 spread and temperature has been explored and researchers have reported that countries were expected to see a decline in new COVID-19 cases during summer and a resurgence during colder months (Notari 2021; Wang 2020; Pawar 2020). This is likely due to higher temperatures and more intense UV radiation in summer more that would support compliance to public health measures to contain SARS-CoV-2 (Chen 2021). Imperial College London were one of the first research groups to incorporate environmental data into epidemiological models of the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 (Smith et al, 2021). They found that, to a certain extent, temperature could significantly change COVID-19 transmission. Their work suggests that lower autumn and winter temperatures may lead to the virus spreading more easily in the absence of policy interventions or behavioural changes.

To factor in periods of low temperature during the COVID-19 pandemic, the COVINFORM project obtained mean daily temperature data from each Metrological Headquarter in the 27 MS and the UK. In order to demonstrate comparability, the data was computed to a binary variable, reporting the proportion of days in which a country had a daily average temperature of less than 15 degrees (typical average autumn temperature or lower).

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Temperature</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK – Proportion of days per year where daily mean temperature is less than 15oC.
Source/s	EU MS & UK – European Climate Assessment & Dataset
Direction	-1

Age of population

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Adult Population</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK

Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU MS – Population divided into age groups • UK – Population divided into age groups
Source/s	EU MS – EUROSTAT UK - OECD
Direction	1

COVID-19 vaccination rate

An effective immunisation rollout offered the most promising prospect of reducing morbidity, mortality and overcoming the COVID-19 pandemic¹³. Studies also suggested some benefit of vaccination and vaccine boosting in reducing transmission of COVID-19^{14,15,16}. Public health officials and policymakers created strategic vaccine-acceptance communications to ensure wide vaccine¹⁷. Once the rollout commenced, the scale and rate of vaccination was reported routinely by national public health surveillance agencies and included information on the total number of vaccinations administered and daily population coverage¹⁸.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>COVID-19 vaccination rate</i>
Reporting period	2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily (Data taken from last recorded day of the year)
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU MS & UK – COVID-19 Vaccine Rate (% population fully vaccinated)
Source/s	EU MS & UK – Our World in Data
Direction	-1

Domain 2: VULNERABILITIES

Sub-domain 2.1: Physical

Hospital beds, Intensive Care Unit beds and Residential beds

Healthcare organizations needed to quickly create surge capacity, defined as the ability of healthcare services to increase their operations in response to a crisis to safely treat an increased inflow of patients. The pandemic's increasing demand directly impacted the limited resources on which healthcare services are built, such as employees and goods, as well as structure and system. Health or physical vulnerability in the COVINFORM risk assessment framework includes both healthcare capacity and the level of clinical vulnerability to COVID-

¹³ Le, T. T., Andreadakis, Z., Kumar, A., Román, R. G., Tollefsen, S., Saville, M., & Mayhew, S. (2020). The COVID-19 vaccine development landscape. *Nat Rev Drug Discov*, 19(5), 305-306.

¹⁴ Tan, S.T., Kwan, A.T., Rodríguez-Barraquer, I. et al. Infectiousness of SARS-CoV-2 breakthrough infections and reinfections during the Omicron wave. *Nat Med* 29, 358–365 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-02138-x>

¹⁵ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-022-02328-0>

¹⁶ Eyre, D. W., Taylor, D., Purver, M., Chapman, D., Fowler, T., Pouwels, K. B., ... & Peto, T. E. (2022). Effect of Covid-19 vaccination on transmission of alpha and delta variants. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 386(8), 744-756.

¹⁷ Chou, W. Y. S., & Budenz, A. (2020). Considering emotion in COVID-19 vaccine communication: addressing vaccine hesitancy and fostering vaccine confidence. *Health communication*, 35(14), 1718-1722.

¹⁸ Mathieu, E., Ritchie, H., Ortiz-Ospina, E., Roser, M., Hasell, J., Appel, C., ... & Rodés-Guirao, L. (2021). A global database of COVID-19 vaccinations. *Nature human behaviour*, 5(7), 947-953.

19 at a population level. COVID-19 brought to light the necessity for a sufficient number of hospital beds and flexibility in their usage (i.e., ventilation and intensive care beds), as well as a sufficient number of medical professionals (doctors and nurses) with the necessary training to deliver the necessary care¹⁹.

Healthcare vulnerabilities can be measured using various metrics and was closely monitored by public health bodies and healthcare organisation over the COVID-19 pandemic. Hospital bed and ICU bed capacity are common healthcare resource metrics to monitor the ability to provide care to inpatients²⁰. ICU beds are defined as beds with critical care equipment (e.g., ventilator) that are adequately staffed by specialized nurses and physicians with critical care training. Hospital beds are defined as beds regularly maintained, staffed, and available for use in public, private, general, and specialized hospitals and rehabilitation centres²¹.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Hospital Beds</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK – Hospital beds (per 100,000 inhabitants)
Source/s	EU MS – EUROSTAT UK - OECD
Direction	-1

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>ICU Beds</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021 (last available year's value taken)
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– ICU beds (per 100,000 inhabitants)
Source/s	Multiple sources across EU MS and UK: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A country-level analysis comparing hospital capacity and utilisation during the first COVID-19 wave across Europe, The variability of critical care bed numbers in Europe OECD
Direction	-1

¹⁹ Ji, Y., Ma, Z., Peppelenbosch, M. P., & Pan, Q. (2020). Potential association between COVID-19 mortality and health-care resource availability. *The Lancet global health*, 8(4), e480.

²⁰ Berger, E., Winkelmann, J., Eckhardt, H., Nimptsch, U., Panteli, D., Reichebner, C., Rombey, T., & Busse, R. (2022). A country-level analysis comparing hospital capacity and utilisation during the first COVID-19 wave across Europe. *Health policy (Amsterdam, Netherlands)*, 126(5), 373–381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2021.11.009>

²¹ <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/en/data-insights/intensive-care-beds-capacity>

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Residential Care Beds</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK – Beds in nursing and residential care facilities (per 1,000 inhabitants)
Source/s	EU MS & UK – OECD Where possible, missing MS gaps filled from EUROSTAT
Direction	-1

Medical (Frontline) Staff

During the COVID-19 pandemic the volatility of the public health crisis resulted in intense pressures for healthcare staff, and many healthcare workers were required to deliver care in specialist environments (i.e., ICU) beyond their primary training²². To accurately determine the number of medical staff within certain specialisms or care settings during the course of the COVID-19 pandemic may be impossible but data has been reported across the EU MS and the UK.

Doctors

Data for this indicator come from the Eurostat data 'physicians by medical speciality'. As outlined in the dataset metadata²³, physicians are classified in three main categories: *generalist medical practitioners*, *specialist medical practitioners* and *medical doctor not further defined*.

Nurses

Nurses are defined as all the "practising" nurses providing direct health services to patients, including self-employed nurses. However, for some countries, due to lack of comparable data, the figures correspond to "professionally active" nurses, including nurses working in the health sector as managers, educators, researchers, etc.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Medical Staff - Doctors</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– Doctors (per 100,000 inhabitants)
Source/s	EU MS – EUROSTAT Where possible, missing MS gaps and UK filled from OECD
Direction	-1

²² Bergman, L., Falk, A. C., Wolf, A., & Larsson, I. M. (2021). Registered nurses' experiences of working in the intensive care unit during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Nursing in critical care*, 26(6), 467-475.

²³ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/Annexes/hlth_res_esms_an1.pdf

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Medical Staff - Nurses</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– Nurses (per 100,000 inhabitants)
Source/s	EU MS – EUROSTAT Where possible, missing MS gaps and UK filled from OECD
Direction	-1

Older Adults and Pre-Existing Health Conditions

Older people and people with chronic pre-existing conditions were reported to be at higher risk of severe COVID-19 disease leading to hospitalisation, admission to intensive care, and death²⁴. Diseases posing an increased clinical risk included diabetes, obesity, hypertension, history of heart failure, ischaemic heart disease, cancer, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), chronic respiratory disease, chronic kidney disease, and immune compromised status. In addition, older age was also reported by global health agencies to be a factor for severe COVID-19 outcomes²⁵, with the greatest proportion of COVID-19 related deaths in older populations²⁶.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Pre-existing health conditions</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS– Longstanding health condition (% population)
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT
Direction	1

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Older adult population</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– Ratio of adults aged over 60 years
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT

²⁴ <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/infectious-disease-topics/z-disease-list/covid-19/facts/clinical-features-and-sequelae>

²⁵ <https://www.who.int/europe/news/item/03-04-2020-statement-older-people-are-at-highest-risk-from-covid-19-but-all-must-act-to-prevent-community-spread>

²⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/rtd/items/680700/en>

	UK - OECD
Direction	1

Sub-domain 2.2: Social

Education Level

Observational studies report that the severity of COVID-19 depends not only on physical conditions as mentioned above but also social determinants of health, such as lower incomes and lower educational level among various populations. In the European population, lower education level was associated with a higher risk of severe COVID-19 cases and COVID-19-related mortality^{27,28}. In part, due to behavioural characteristics, such as an inability to adapt working conditions and therefore reduce physical contact.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Education level</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU MS - Low levels of educational attainment (ISCED 2011 classification) • UK – Percentage of population whose highest level educational attainment is less than NQF level 2 or above
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT UK – GOV.UK
Direction	1

Rural vs. Urban and Population Density

Population density and infrastructure played a key role in the transmission and effects of SARS-CoV2 in terms of morbidity and mortality. In the EU and UK, densely populated urban areas were the hardest hit in the first half of 2020, but as social distancing measures were introduced, rates dropped^{29,30}. However, from mid-2020 rural areas were seen to be impacted to a larger extent. Various reasons were attributed to increased risk in rural areas,

²⁷ Drefahl, S., Wallace, M., Mussino, E., Aradhya, S., Kolk, M., Brandén, M., ... & Andersson, G. (2020). A population-based cohort study of socio-demographic risk factors for COVID-19 deaths in Sweden. *Nature communications*, 11(1), 5097.

²⁸ Lüdecke, D., & Von Dem Knesebeck, O. (2020). Protective behavior in course of the COVID-19 outbreak—survey results from Germany. *Frontiers in public health*, 8, 572561.

²⁸ Tamme, P. (2020). Social distancing, population density, and spread of COVID-19 in England: a longitudinal study. *BJGP open*, 4(3).

³⁰ Medica, M. (2020). COVID-19 mortality rates in the European Union, Switzerland, and the UK: effect of timeliness, lockdown rigidity, and population density.

specifically limited access to public health and specialist medical professionals³¹, higher proportions of older dwellers³² and limited digital infrastructure impacting remote working³³.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Ratio of Rural vs. Urban Population</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– Population by sex, age, citizenship, labour status and degree of urbanisation
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT UK – World Bank
Direction	-1

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Population Density</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS - Population density by NUTS 3 region UK– Population density
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT UK – World Bank
Direction	1

Gender

Whilst men were more likely to be infected with SARS-CoV-2 and more likely to die from it³⁴, women’s lives were more greatly affected in terms of social consequences. A report by the Institute for Fiscal Studies found that mothers in the UK were 15 times more likely than fathers to have either quit their job or lost it during the lockdown³⁵. Women are more likely to be “essential workers”, approximately 76% of care workers in the EU are women, 82% of supermarket cashiers and 95% of domestic cleaners and home help, are women³⁶. In addition, during the COVID-19 pandemic, and with the introduction of “lockdowns”, more women lost their lives to domestic violence³⁷.

³¹ Apostolopoulos, N., Liargovas, P., Sklias, P., & Apostolopoulos, S. (2021). Healthcare enterprises and public policies on COVID-19: Insights from the Greek rural areas. *Strategic Change*, 30(2), 127-136.

³² Kashnitsky, I., & Aburto, J. M. (2020). COVID-19 in unequally ageing European regions. *World development*, 136, 105170.

³³ Esteban-Navarro, M. Á., García-Madurga, M. Á., Morte-Nadal, T., & Nogales-Bocio, A. I. (2020, December). The rural digital divide in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic in Europe—recommendations from a scoping review. In *Informatics* (Vol. 7, No. 4, p. 54). MDPI.

³⁴ Pérez-López, F. R., Tajada, M., Savirón-Cornudella, R., Sánchez-Prieto, M., Chedraui, P., & Terán, E. (2020). Coronavirus disease 2019 and gender-related mortality in European countries: A meta-analysis. *Maturitas*, 141, 59–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.maturitas.2020.06.017>

³⁵ <https://www.local.gov.uk/age-and-gender-impact-covid-19>

³⁶ <https://eige.europa.eu/newsroom/covid-19/essential-workers>

³⁷ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/society/20201119STO92007/orange-the-world-no-to-violence-against-women>

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Female Population</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU MS - Population on 1 January by age and sex • UK– National mid-year population estimates for the UK and its constituent countries by administrative area, age and sex
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT UK – OECD
Direction	1

Migrant Population

Research from several countries have revealed a much greater risk of infection and adverse outcomes from COVID-19 among Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic (BAME) groups³⁸, compared to the native white population in the same countries³⁹. These adverse outcomes are likely the result of a complex interaction of socioeconomic disadvantage influencing exposure to SARS-CoV-2 and underlying health status, that predisposes to severe illness⁴⁰.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Migrant Population</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU MS - Immigration by age group, sex and level of human development of the country of citizenship • UK - Long-term international immigration
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT UK - Office for National Statistics UK (ONS)
Direction	1

Civic Participation

Civic participation is the involvement of members of society or communities in local, state, and national government. It can include voting, activism, volunteering, and community

³⁸ Bhatia, M. (2020). COVID-19 and BAME Group in the United Kingdom. *The International Journal of Community and Social Development*, 2(2), 269-272.

³⁹ Hargreaves, S., Hayward, S. E., Noori, T., McKee, M., & Kumar, B. (2021). COVID-19: counting migrants in. *The Lancet*, 398(10296), 211-212.

⁴⁰ Hayward, S. E., Deal, A., Cheng, C., Crawshaw, A., Orcutt, M., Vandrevalla, T. F., ... & Hargreaves, S. (2021). Clinical outcomes and risk factors for COVID-19 among migrant populations in high-income countries: a systematic review. *Journal of migration and health*, 3, 100041.

engagement but at the simplest level, “freedom of opinion and expression is effectively guaranteed”⁴¹. The level of civic participation became increasingly important during the COVID-19 pandemic⁴². Bottom-up approaches, where the community is a resource and an active partner, became critical for building trust and addressing inequalities, particularly in terms of COVID-19 vaccine uptake and compliance to social interventions^{43,44}.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Civic Participation</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– Degree of Civic Participation (%)
Source/s	EU MS & UK – World Justice Project – World Bank
Direction	-1

Sub-Domain 2.3 Economic

Economic vulnerability can be defined as ‘*the risk a country faces when encountering a shock*’⁴⁵.

Gross Domestic Product - purchasing power parities (GDP-PPP)

GDP is a measure of the strength of a country’s economy. Defined as ‘*the total monetary or market value of all the finished goods and services produced within a country in a specific time period*’⁴⁶. There are various reporting metrics for GDP, however, ‘purchasing power parities’ (PPP) allows for comparison across countries. PPPs are ‘*price relatives that show the ratio of the prices in national currencies of the same good or service in different countries*’⁴⁷.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>GDP</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– GDP – PPP (constant, 2017)
Source/s	EU MS & UK – World Bank

⁴¹ https://worldjusticeproject.org/sites/default/files/documents/ROLIndex2017-2018_Variables_FINAL.pdf

⁴² Waeterloos, C., De Meulenaere, J., Walrave, M., & Ponnet, K. (2021). Tackling COVID-19 from below: civic participation among online neighbourhood network users during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Online information review*, 45(4), 777-794.

⁴³ Jalloh, M. F., Nur, A. A., Nur, S. A., Winters, M., Bedson, J., Pedi, D., Prybylski, D., Namageyo-Funa, A., Hageman, K. M., Baker, B. J., Jalloh, M. B., Eng, E., Nordenstedt, H., & Hakim, A. J. (2021). Behaviour adoption approaches during public health emergencies: implications for the COVID-19 pandemic and beyond. *BMJ global health*, 6(1), e004450. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2020-004450>

⁴⁴ Waeterloos, C., De Meulenaere, J., Walrave, M., & Ponnet, K. (2021). Tackling COVID-19 from below: civic participation among online neighbourhood network users during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Online information review*, 45(4), 777-794.

⁴⁵ Noy, I., & Yonson, R. (2018). Economic vulnerability and resilience to natural hazards: A survey of concepts and measurements. *Sustainability*, 10(8), 2850.

⁴⁶ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/g/gdp.asp>

⁴⁷ <https://www.oecd.org/sdd/prices-ppp/purchasingpowerparities-frequentlyaskedquestionsfaqs.htm>

Direction	-1
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Poverty

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed to a greater extent the vulnerability of poor populations. Poverty interacts with health in many ways and research has shown that those living in poverty are more likely to have chronic illnesses⁴⁸. In addition, poverty impacts a person's resilience, straining their capabilities and opportunities⁴⁹.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Population living in Poverty</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– % of people with an equivalised disposable income (after social transfer) below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT UK – GOV.UK
Direction	1

Income Inequality

Income is also associated with health: people in the bottom 40% of the income distribution are almost twice as likely to report poor health than those in the top 20%⁵⁰. Early findings reported by Frank Elgar et al., (2020) demonstrated through time series analysis showed that COVID-19-related mortality was positively related to income inequality, trust and confidence in state institutions⁵¹.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Income Inequality</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– Inequality of income distribution (S80/S20 ratio)
Source/s	EU MS – EUROSTAT UK - Office for National Statistics UK (ONS)
Direction	1

⁴⁸ Callander, E. J., Schofield, D. J., & Shrestha, R. N. (2013). Chronic health conditions and poverty: a cross-sectional study using a multidimensional poverty measure. *BMJ open*, 3(11), e003397.

⁴⁹ Béné, C., Newsham, A., Davies, M., Ulrichs, M., & Godfrey-Wood, R. (2014). Resilience, poverty and development. *Journal of international development*, 26(5), 598-623.

⁵⁰ Tinson, A. (2020). Living in poverty was bad for your health before COVID-19. The Health Foundation.

⁵¹ Elgar, F. J., Stefaniak, A., & Wohl, M. J. (2020). The trouble with trust: Time-series analysis of social capital, income inequality, and COVID-19 deaths in 84 countries. *Social science & medicine*, 263, 113365.

Precarious Employment

Those in precarious employment, characterised by poorly paid employment, employment insecurity (e.g., temporary or zero-hour contracts), and limited rights and protection, were greatly impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic⁵². Women, migrant workers, low skilled workers, and young people are more likely than others to be precariously employed⁵³. Many employees experienced cycles of employment, and then unemployment, especially during times of lockdown⁵⁴.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Precarious Employment</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none">EU MS & UK– Industries known to be affected by COVID-19 policy measures - Arts and Recreation, Construction, Accommodation and Food, Transport and Storage and Wholesale and Retail
Source/s	EU MS – EUROSTAT (CEDEFOP) UK - Office for National Statistics UK (ONS)
Direction	1

Sub-domain 2.4: Information

Information and communication inequalities are mediating factors in the exacerbated health disparities observed in vulnerable groups during the pandemic. The following factors were considered important in understanding the level of access populations had to public health information; and as a tool to reduce social isolation during times during lockdowns.

Digital Skills and Access

Societal differences in access and use of digital technologies are commonly referred to as the 'digital divide' and disproportionately affect the health of disadvantaged communities such as ethnic minorities, rural populations, the elderly and residents of care homes⁵⁵. Lower levels of digital access and skills further isolated vulnerable populations and increased health risks as community-based healthcare delivery largely moved to a telehealth model (ibid.).

⁵² Matilla-Santander, N., Ahonen, E., Albin, M., Baron, S., Bolibar, M., Bosmans, K., ... & All Members of the PWR Study Consortium. (2021). COVID-19 and precarious employment: consequences of the evolving crisis. *International Journal of Health Services*, 51(2), 226-228.

⁵³ Julià, M., Vanroelen, C., Bosmans, K., Van Aerden, K., & Benach, J. (2017). Precarious employment and quality of employment in relation to health and well-being in Europe. *International Journal of Health Services*, 47(3), 389-409.

⁵⁴ <https://australianinstitute.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Shock-Troops-of-the-Pandemic.pdf>

⁵⁵ Ramsetty, A., & Adams, C. (2020). Impact of the digital divide in the age of COVID-19. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 27(7), 1147-1148.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Digital Skills</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– % Individuals with low levels of digital skills
Source/s	EU MS – EUROSTAT UK – Lloyd's Bank Essential Digital Skills Index
Direction	-1

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Digital Access</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– % Access to Household ICT
Source/s	EU MS – EUROSTAT UK – GOV.UK
Direction	-1

Trust in Government

The level of trust in the communication actors was a key determinant in compliance to public health measures⁵⁶. Furthermore, research has shown a direct and indirect association of good governance practices and the public's trust in government via perceived government response on COVID-19⁵⁷. Results also showed that government agency's delivery of quality information on social media positively shapes public trust in government (ibid.).

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Trust in Government</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Bi-annual (except for 2020 where only one survey was conducted)
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– Do you tend to trust or not trust your National Government? %
Source/s	EU MS & UK– Eurobarometer Survey
Direction	-1

⁵⁶ Shanka, M. S., & Menebo, M. M. (2022). When and how trust in government leads to compliance with COVID-19 precautionary measures. *Journal of Business Research*, 139, 1275-1283.

⁵⁷ Mansoor, M. (2021). Citizens' trust in government as a function of good governance and government agency's provision of quality information on social media during COVID-19. *Government information quarterly*, 38(4), 101597.

DOMAIN 3: CONSEQUENCES

Sub-domain 3.1: Health

Excess mortality (Recorded for COVID-19 years - 2020 and 2021)

Excess mortality is a term used in epidemiology that refers to the number of deaths from all causes during a crisis above and beyond what would be expected to see under 'normal' conditions⁵⁸. In this case, we're interested in how the number of deaths during the COVID-19 pandemic compares to the deaths that would have been expected had the pandemic not occurred.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Excess Deaths</i>
Reporting period	2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Cumulative
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none">EU MS– Cumulative deaths from all causes compared to projection based on previous years (per million people)
Source/s	EU MS and UK– Our World in Data
Direction	1

Hospital Occupancy and ICU admissions (COVID-19-related)

The direct impact of COVID-19 on healthcare systems was closely monitored during the pandemic, using key resource metrics (i.e., hospital bed occupancy rates). Public health officials closely monitored this data to identify a drop in the system's capacity (i.e., bed shortages), which in turn prompted government responses (i.e., lockdown measures)⁵⁹.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>COVID-19 Hospital Occupancy</i>
Reporting period	2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS
Reporting format	Daily – Annual average calculated
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none">EU MS– Data on hospital occupancy for COVID-19
Source/s	EU MS – ECDC
Direction	1

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>COVID-19 ICU Occupancy</i>

⁵⁸ <https://www.kingsfund.org.uk/blog/2023/03/when-death-excess-death-getting-behind-numbers>

⁵⁹ Verelst, F., Kuylen, E., & Beutels, P. (2020). Indications for healthcare surge capacity in European countries facing an exponential increase in coronavirus disease (COVID-19) cases, March 2020. *Eurosurveillance*, 25(13), 2000323.

Reporting period	2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS
Reporting format	Daily – Annual average calculated
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS - Data on ICU admission rates and current occupancy for COVID-19
Source/s	EU MS - ECDC
Direction	1

COVID-19 related deaths

The ultimate consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic is the loss of life. COVID-19 was ranked as a leading cause of death; and at certain times, it was the leading cause of death⁶⁰. Mortality risk was determined by age, with the risk of COVID-19 death highest in older adult populations and lowest in the young (ibid). Definitions and reporting of COVID-19-related deaths varied across EU member states and the UK, particularly in the early stage in the pandemic. Such as whether someone ever had a positive test, had one within a defined period before death, or did not have a test but had symptoms consistent with COVID-19⁶¹

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>COVID-19 death rate</i>
Reporting period	2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Cumulative
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– Number of confirmed deaths from COVID-19
Source/s	EU MS & UK– Our World in Data
Direction	1

As all the above mentioned indicators in this subdomain are related to the pandemic, the data is only recorded for the years 2020 and 2021. So as to have a baseline figure in 2019 to compare to, the following two indicators have been used as a proxy measure to inspect hospital occupancy and resource utilisation prior to the pandemic.

Curative Care Bed Occupancy

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Curative Care Bed Occupancy</i>
Reporting period	2019
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly

⁶⁰ <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/article-abstract/2774464>

⁶¹ Karanikolos, M., & McKee, M. (2020). How comparable is COVID-19 mortality across countries?. Eurohealth, 26(2), 45-50.

Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– % of inpatient curative care beds occupied
Source/s	EU MS & UK– EUROSTAT
Direction	1

Average Length of Hospital Stay

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Average Length of Hospital Stay</i>
Reporting period	2019
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– Average length of stay (ALOS) is computed by dividing the number of hospital days (or bed-days or in-patient days) from the date of admission in an in-patient institution (date of discharge minus date of admission) by the number of discharges (including deaths) during the year.
Source/s	EU MS & UK– EUROSTAT
Direction	1

Sub-domain 3.2: Social

Food Insecurity

A person is considered “food secure” when they have the physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life⁶². COVID-19 threatened food security in some developed countries and further impacted human security⁶³.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Food Insecurity</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population (%)
Source/s	EU MS & UK– Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)
Direction	1

Crime

⁶² https://www.fao.org/fileadmin/templates/faoitally/documents/pdf/pdf_Food_Security_Cocept_Note.pdf

⁶³ <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/cread/article/view/202191>

The COVID-19 pandemic and government responses to limit social contact have had a significant impact on patterns of crime⁶⁴. Certain police reported crimes have declined, such as household burglaries, however, there has been increased reporting of domestic violence⁶⁵ and online fraud. Survey conducted in the UK have shown the crime patterns returned to typical incidence rates following lockdown periods⁶⁶.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Crime</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– Police recorded crimes
Source/s	EU MS – EUROSTAT UK– Scotland Public Health Observatory , Police Service of Northern Ireland (PSNI) , Office for National Statistics UK (England and Wales crime)
Direction	1

Loss of Education

Beyond health-related consequences, one of the most notably impacts of the pandemic was the loss of education in children. The full extent of the disruption in learning and development will only be understood in the coming decades. Before the end of 2020 the Department for Education (UK), found a learning loss of up to 2 months in reading in both primary and secondary pupils, based on assessments of more than 400,000 pupils⁶⁷. Again, and as per the compounded vulnerability of those already living precariously, the lack of educational progress made is proportionally greater in children living in persistent poverty, attributable to a lack of digital access and technology, and adequate home supports⁶⁸.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>School Closures</i>
Reporting period	2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily - Annual average calculated
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK - Severity of school closure - 0 (No School closures), 1 (Localized School Closures), 2 (National School Closures)
Source/s	EU MS & UK– Response2covid19.org
Direction	1

⁶⁴ Nivette, A.E., Zahnow, R., Aguilar, R. *et al.* A global analysis of the impact of COVID-19 stay-at-home restrictions on crime. *Nat Hum Behav* 5, 868–877 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-021-01139-z>

⁶⁵ Bradbury-Jones, C., & Isham, L. (2020). The pandemic paradox: the consequences of COVID-19 on domestic violence. 2020. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 12.

⁶⁶ <https://blog.ons.gov.uk/2021/11/04/understanding-the-impact-of-the-pandemic-on-levels-of-crime-in-england-and-wales/>

⁶⁷ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/pupils-progress-in-the-2020-to-2022-academic-years>

⁶⁸ <https://epi.org.uk/publications-and-research/education-in-england-annual-report-2020/>

Sub-domain 3.3: Economic

The pandemic has impacted the economy in many ways, as described above. Lockdown restrictions, temporary closure of businesses to limit movement, the economic impact has been severe⁶⁹, and many countries are experiencing financial crises⁷⁰. The following indicators have been incorporated into the COVINFORM risk assessment framework, to quantify the economic consequences in Europe and the UK.

Unemployment Rates

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Unemployment Rate</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none">EU MS - Unemployment by sex, age and duration of unemployment (1 000)UK– Unemployment rate (aged 16 and over, seasonally adjusted): %
Source/s	EU MS – EUROSTAT UK– Office for National Statistics UK (ONS)
Direction	1

Household Disposable Income

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Household Disposable Income</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none">EU MS & UK– Median Household Disposable Income (PPP)
Source/s	EU MS – EUROSTAT UK - Office for National Statistics UK (ONS)
Direction	-1

Social Protection

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Social Protection Benefits</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly

⁶⁹ Pak, A., Adegboye, O. A., Adekunle, A. I., Rahman, K. M., McBryde, E. S., & Eisen, D. P. (2020). Economic consequences of the COVID-19 outbreak: the need for epidemic preparedness. *Frontiers in public health*, 8, 241.

⁷⁰ <https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/eu-economy-after-covid-19-implications-economic-governance>

Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK – Total expenditure on social protection benefits by type (% of GDP)
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT UK - OECD
Direction	-1

Sub-domain 3.4: Environmental

As reported OECD, the COVID-19 pandemic and implemented responses have significant effects on economic activity and the structure of the economy⁷¹. The latter plays a key role in how economic effects translate into effects on environmental pressures. The environmental consequences that are linked to energy use seen a decline in 2020 of 7-8%, followed by a recovery to 2-3% below the pre-COVID baseline projection (ibid). This includes emissions of Greenhouse Gases, air pollutants and fossil fuel materials use.

Other environmental pressures have a different set of economic influence, and have a notable pattern of impacts. Emissions of particulate matter (PM2.5), which includes black carbon and organic carbon, are linked to transport (heavily affected) and residential activities (less affected) (ibid.). Both GHG emissions and PM2.5 have been included in the COVINFORM risk assessment model.

Exposure to Pollution

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Pollution (PM2.5)</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Annual Mean
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK– Fine Particulate Matter (PM2.5)
Source/s	EU MS & UK - European Environmental Agency UK – GOV.UK
Direction	1

Greenhouse Gas Emissions

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>GHG Emissions</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly

⁷¹ <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/the-long-term-environmental-implications-of-covid-19-4b7a9937/>

Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK – Greenhouse gas emissions (tonnes per capita)
Source/s	EU MS & UK – Our World in Data
Direction	1

DOMAIN 4: RESILIENCE

Resilience is “the ability of a system or organization to react to and recover from disturbances at an early stage, with minimal effect on the dynamic stability”⁷². Resilience involves the ability of a complex system to absorb the “shocks” gracefully and rebound in a controlled manner to a level of performance equivalent of beyond pre-disturbance (ibid.).

Sub-domain 4.1: Ability to recover

Government Health Spending

Given the COVID-19 pandemic shocked the healthcare systems across the world, the level of investment prior to and during the pandemic directly influences their ability to recover.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Government Health Spending</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK – Compulsory Government Health Spending (% GDP)
Source/s	EU MS & UK - OECD
Direction	-1

Investments - Gross fixed capital formation

GFCF dropped dramatically across all EU countries and the UK during the pandemic, although with different intensities across MS⁷³. The economic policy responses mitigated the impact of the pandemic and supported recovery. Total investment in EU countries declined due to high uncertainty in the economy. And household savings and household financial net worth have increased, while the impact of the crisis on household debt has been limited (ibid.). These averages, however, mask divergent trends, with both wealth and savings increasing faster among the wealthy⁷⁴.

⁷² Johnsen S. (2010). Resilience in Risk Analysis and Risk Assessment. Critical Infrastructure Protection IV: Fourth Annual IFIP WG 11.10 International Conference on Critical Infrastructure Protection, ICCIP 2010, Washington, DC, USA, March 15-17, 2010, Revised Selected Papers, 342, 215–227. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16806-2_15

⁷³ Licchetta, M., & Meyermans, E. (2022). Gross Fixed Capital Formation in the Euro Area During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Intereconomics*, 57(4), 238–246. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10272-022-1058-1>

⁷⁴ <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/4d28b126-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/4d28b126-en>

Gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), also called "investment", is defined as the acquisition of produced assets.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Investments</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK – Gross fixed capital formation (% of GDP)
Source/s	EU MS & UK – World Bank
Direction	-1

General Government Debt

Government finances offer an indication of the health of national economies. The COVID-19 pandemic drove economic recessions globally in 2020 however by 2021, deficits began to decline again⁷⁵. The economic slump caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, resulted in a drop in GDP and the expenditure measures to contain the economic and social impact of the pandemic had a strong impact on the EU MS and UK economic profile and ability to recover (ibid.).

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>General Government Debt</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK – Consolidated general government gross debt at nominal value, outstanding at the end of the year (%GDP)
Source/s	EU MS - EUROSTAT UK - Office for National Statistics UK (ONS)
Direction	1

Corruption Perception Index (CPI)

The CPI ranks countries around the world by their perceived levels of public sector corruption, scoring on a scale of 0 (highly corrupt) to 100 (very clean). Corruption affects governments' ability to protect citizens and reduces public trust, resulting in increased and more difficult-to-control security concerns.

Attribute	Description
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⁷⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Government_finance_statistics#Introduction

Indicator name	<i>Corruption Perception Index</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK – CPI Score - 0 (highly corrupt) to 100 (very clean)
Source/s	EU MS & UK – Transparency.org
Direction	-1

Vaccine Affordability

Vaccine equity means that vaccines should be allocated across all countries based on needs and regardless of their economic status. Globally, the distribution of vaccines is shaped by challenging political, economic, social, diplomatic, and health-related matters. Therefore, accurate and up-to-date data and information are critical components in guiding the understanding of vaccine equity and highlight blind spots.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Vaccine Affordability</i>
Reporting period	2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK
Reporting format	No time period specified
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU MS & UK – Cost of vaccinating 40% of population as percent of current health expenditure (CHE) per capita in US\$
Source/s	EU MS & UK – UNDP.org
Direction	1

Sub-domain 4.2: Ability to adapt

Economic and Public Health Measures

COVID-19 has had a significant impact on global public health and economies. To appropriately respond, a number of containment and mitigation measures were implemented, with the goal of mitigating surges of patients in hospitals and safeguarding the most vulnerable persons from infection, including the elderly and those with co-morbidities. Strategies for achieving these targets vary, but they are typically based on national risk assessments, which include estimates of the number of patients requiring hospital admission. A list of economic measures (e.g., income support, rent freezes, tax credits) and health measures (e.g., masks, curfew, domestic lockdown, state of emergency).

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Economic and Non-Pharmaceutical Health interventions</i>
Reporting period	2020 and 2021
Geographic Coverage	EU MS and UK

Reporting format	Daily – Annual average calculated
Definition and Reporting criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU MS & UK – Intensity of economic interventions (Import/Export Support, Tax credits, cash transfers, tax delays, lowered central bank interest rates, wage support, credit schemes) and non-pharmaceutical health interventions (Global score based on policies for masks, curfew, domestic lockdown, state of emergency) in response to COVID-19 pandemic • Measured as severity of interventions where - 0 (No interventions) to 1 (all interventions are strict)
Source/s	EU MS & UK – Response2covid19.org
Direction	-1